

Monograph for Generic Code for Vision

Based on HappyLanesColor colouring method

Éva Szűts-Nowsky

I have not sought to explain every approach in detail in this material, but rather to highlight the fact that visual perception is the fundamental, informal starting point of human behavior, and consequently, the indisputable merit of a visual method suitable for schematization, so-called coding, is that it can be the subject of multidisciplinary analysis. Therefore, its aim is to provide everyone, regardless of their field of expertise, with an insight into the exciting world of vision, beyond the presentation of the method.

Forward

“It is a great pleasure to write this foreword. The following monograph summarises many decades of inspirational work at the intersection of art therapy, neuroaesthetics, educational psychology and theoretical neurobiology. The neuroscientific backdrop to this monograph is a first principles account of self-organisation called the free energy principle.

In applying the free energy principle to active engagement with the sensorium, one is often drawn to the fact that we author our own sensorium. Put simply, the things that we perceive are a consequence of the way we act (Gregory, 1980; Helmholtz, 1866/1962; Parr and Friston, 2019; Parr et al., 2022). This is true at many levels. For example, when we move our eyes — four times a second — we visually palpate the world in a particular way; sampling the visual scene to resolve uncertainty about the cause of our sensations, e.g. visual objects (Friston et al., 2012; Wurtz et al., 2011). This enactive aspect of scene construction is often explained in terms of active inference; very much in the spirit of Helmholtz’s unconscious inference (Parr et al., 2022). In other words, we are constantly trying to find the best explanations or hypotheses that explain our sensory input. This is often called inference to the best explanation (Seth, 2015). This has to be the case because we can only sample the world through our sensory epithelia within our eyes and ears.

In a similar vein, not only do we carefully choose what to look at — we also actively construct what we see; whether this is a movement of our body or the artefacts we create. These artefacts can range from paintings through to architecture; in the spirit of designer environments and niche construction (that could include cultural niche construction and language itself) (Constant et al., 2018; Veissiere et al., 2019). The underlying theme here is that we are the authors of what we see and — from the perspective of active inference — to ‘see’ is to ‘look’.

This monograph is about a paradigm called Colouring Lanes. Colouring Lanes can be read in many different ways. It could be read as a game. It could be read as an educational guide. It could be read as a vehicle for art therapy. It could be read as an experimental laboratory of visual sentience. At its simplest, Colouring Lanes provides a context and substrate for people — usually children — to exercise their skills in active inference and, in particular, active vision. Colouring Lanes does this by appealing to the fundamentals of active inference, which we can now briefly rehearse.

Active inference is an application of the free energy principle to natural kinds, such as ourselves. It is a first principles account of an active engagement with the world that rests upon minimising surprise or, equivalently, maximising the evidence for internal (a.k.a., generative) models of the sensed world. So what does that mean? In brief, it means our brains are constructive organs that generate predictions of what we would see, if we had the right explanation for the causes of our sensations. These predictions are then used to create a measure of surprise in the form of a prediction error. Prediction errors are formed by comparing what we predict we would sense with what we actually sense. If we have the right explanation — e.g., “I am looking at your face” — then there should be no prediction error and surprise is minimal.

Conversely, if we have the wrong idea or explanation in mind, then surprise will be high and the ensuing prediction errors can be used to — literally — change our mind (through a process called predictive coding or Bayesian belief updating)(Friston and Kiebel, 2009; Rao and Ballard, 1999). Effectively, this means finding a better explanation that resolves prediction errors, which can be read as perceptual inference or inference to the best explanation.

Crucially, we can resolve prediction errors in two ways. We can either make predictions more like sensations or, we can make our sensations more like our predictions — by moving our eyes or acting upon the world in a way that realises our predictions. From a mathematical perspective, the surprise in question is the negative evidence for our models of the world. This means that to minimise surprise is to seek evidence for our models and predictions. In the setting of active inference, we can create this evidence by realising what is envisaged in our minds. Put simply, this would be like imagining what it would look and feel like to stroke something. These intentions can then be realised by our muscles to produce visual and proprioceptive sensations we predicted. In short, to minimise surprise — technically, to minimise variational free energy — is to maximise or seek evidence for our generative models, which is sometimes known as self-evidencing (Hohwy, 2016; Hohwy, 2025).

A crucial aspect of active inference is how we choose what to do next. If we are the kinds of creatures that minimise surprise, then we are compelled to choose actions that minimise expected surprise. So, what is expected surprise? Expected surprise can be read in two ways; both of which underwrite our choice behaviour. Mathematically, expected surprise corresponds to uncertainty. This means that we act in a way to resolve uncertainty. For example, looking at a part of the visual scene that provides the greatest amount of information about the cause of visual sensations. The other reading of expected surprise is that we tend to avoid those outcomes and consequences that would be surprising, given the kind of thing that we are (e.g., acting in a way that caused pain for ourselves or others).

Colouring Lanes focuses on the first imperative; namely, the minimisation of uncertainty. This is described in many ways; including, intrinsic value, intrinsic motivation, epistemic value, epistemic affordance, exploration, Bayesian surprise, and, crucially, curiosity (Berlyne, 1950, 1954; Friston et al., 2017; Schmidhuber, 2006). Mathematically, it is scored in terms of the expected information gain that would ensue on committing to a particular course of action. In brief, it is this imperative that makes us curious and enables us to make sense of the world in the most efficient way possible. This sense-making is subject to certain constraints.

An interesting constraint is that we are compelled to find an accurate explanation that is as simple as possible. Mathematically, this follows because the evidence (i.e., negative surprise) can always be expressed as accuracy minus complexity (Penny, 2012; Penny et al., 2004). This

means that the imperative to minimise surprise compels us to find the simplest explanation that provides an accurate account of what we sense. These dual aspects of active engagement with the world are the pillars of Colouring Lanes.

Colouring Lanes, in essence, provides an opportunity to create visual art that realises our predictions and resolves uncertainty about the different explanations for some minimal (line) cues the visual field. Crucially, it leverages the imperative to minimise uncertainty while, at the same time, affording the opportunity to create simple yet accurate explanations for the line cues in question. Practically, this entails building images of scenes by colouring between the lines in a particular way: in a way that forces the practitioner to commit to a particular hypothesis or explanation for each putative image.

In short, Colouring Lanes offers the opportunity to resolve uncertainty by committing to a particular pattern of colouring that is deliberately ambiguous; thereby affording the opportunity to resolve uncertainty or ambiguity. This opportunity is realised by constructing a coloured scene that provides a parsimonious yet ambiguity-resolving explanation for the lanes provided. In some senses, this laboratory or ‘gymnasium’ for active perception could be likened to music therapy or education; inviting mastery over ambiguity resolution in the service of creating simple and coherent scenes that are readily predictable by others and, crucially, the self.”

Karl Friston

Chapter 1.

The essence of the HappyLanesColor visual method

The essence of the method is based on a special relationship between colouring lanes and drawings. The system of colouring lanes works as image in image, that is the drawings defined by its contours and the coloured interconnected patches constitute the task as colouring lanes. In fact, the missing parts have to be filled with the colours provided.

Thus, the rule does not change, but the subject matter, the complexity of the drawings, and the special system of colouring lanes assigned to them can provide endless variations. The colouring sheets can be sorted in order of difficulty according to various approaches and goals.

The image-in-image principle is thus an opportunity to distinguish the picture to be coloured from the rule, the primary image-message from the distracting or adversarial pictures ("stickers"). The fundamental question, then, is how far you allow yourself to be influenced by the particular direction of the dominant coloured spots, or you can follow the less dominant shapes that are defined only by their outlines. The colouring lane may have the shape of a flower, but after the solution one gets a house. And can you foresee that a house will be the solution? Can you notice the essence beyond the disturbing cavalcade of the coloured surface?

To understand the essence of the method, you need to analyse how the colouring lanes work first through a simple example.

Imagine a room that is completely white from the floor through the walls to the ceiling with a very simple white light source. If you have to spend a long time in it, you will soon feel very uncomfortable due to the environment lacking any stimuli. However, if you do the opposite and stay in a room filled with a variety of small, colourful newspaper clippings stuck on everywhere, and in addition, you have to select, for example, pictures of cars. The task is almost hopeless and you rather decide to do nothing. You choose a behaviour of avoidance, i.e. ignore the task. Thus, in these two extreme cases, you are exposed to either very few or to many environmental stimuli. Compared to this, your primary goal is always to achieve a state of equilibrium in your current position and state, and according to your other abilities at that specific moment.

How does this work in this case at hand? There's a drawing with colouring lanes. This task has something to do with your abilities, motivations, curiosity, your current emotional state, and so on. You have an overview of the whole picture; you can see for example that it depicts a group of buildings.

There are parts of the picture that are clear. You can see that the colouring lanes on the roofs are red, so it is obvious that all the missing parts of the roof waiting to be coloured are to be filled in with red.

However, in the worksheet, you can find details where the image is made up of more complex systems of forms behind one another. Some details are not obvious, so you need to check what the colouring lane shows you for the small details in large shapes.

The information concerned is sometimes enough to solve the issue, but sometimes it is too much or just too little for you. For example, if for this simple roof there are more than one red colouring lanes, then there is too much information for the solution. However, if only one, in addition an opposite, colouring lane is provided for a complex network of shapes, as a distracting image, then, in order to colour the image correctly, you have to follow the instructions of the colouring band almost step by step to find the right colour for each shape.

In conclusion, the essence of the method is that it always keeps you at the level of your own while you are finding the solution. Not in the white room, but not in the poster room either. You are free to choose the solution. If the colouring lane "over explains" the solution to you, then you step over it and let your creative imagination work, but if you find it harder to make sense of the network of various shapes, following the rule step by step will help you out. This will ensure a dynamic equilibrium whereby neither a behaviour of avoidance nor a feeling of discomfort due to an environment lacking any stimuli will occur. In other words, the method will provide you with the opportunity to increase or decrease the level of stimulation in your environment to reach your own level of equilibrium or arousal, which is most needed and optimal for you at that moment, by decreasing or increasing it. You also have the opportunity

to manage your power, your capabilities in the way that best suits you. A colouring task includes easier and harder parts alike. If you are getting a little tired you can find the islands of relaxation e.g. by colouring a big red roof, but after that you are almost waiting for something more challenging, because you wouldn't be able to spend more time with such a boring part, would you?

Of course, in order to understand and imagine the above, it is also important to look at what is happening in the information processing “computer” of your brain. When you are confronted with new information, the brain's search for the right answer begins. It is realised by sending the information concerned to the highest level of the brain hierarchy like a prediction. If this particular prediction is not correct, it becomes a "prediction error" and therefore gets back to some lower levels the right solution, connection or answer is going to be matched for it. If this process is successful, it will be returned to the highest level and, will be put in the right place within the stored information as a correct piece of data. This way, the relationship between input and predictions is such that, in order to achieve the appropriate equilibrium, you either change the input to fulfil the prediction or alter the prediction to become manageable, or else, processable input for you.

In other words, if the stimulus in your environment is low and your level of equilibrium or arousal, is low, then you must somehow raise the external stimulus level, but if it is unmanageably high, you must reduce it. These processes can work by aligning your actions and your perceptions. How does this work for the method? There are always two questions. What detail of the drawing to be coloured and what is the colouring lane? What should you follow? Your brain always sends this prediction. Drawing shape or colouring lane? Or else, which big whole the shapes to be coloured are parts of? Where does each one belong to? Of course, you can see the whole picture, i.e. what it is depicting, even in this form of “scribbled” with the colouring lanes, but you may not be able to immediately identify every detail as part of the large shape during the process of problem solving. A lot of things happen in a picture. You face an avalanche forest of shapes, colours, drawing directions (curves, concentric circles, parallels ..), so there are countless predictions circulating between hierarchical levels. Pictures in the picture. Colouring lanes in the drawings that confuse you.

In this case, the function of the colouring lanes is to provide a visual representation of the free energies. Therefore your brain operates along your routine vision, routine solutions. So, if the coloured, wavy, curved stripes of the colouring lanes are fixed in your brain as the dominant image, even though it has a straight, vertical-horizontal line of view of a building complex, you tend to follow the wavy curves of the dominant colouring lanes. The colouring lanes act as distracting or conflicting images, confuse you and you will make wrong decisions when trying to solve the task. Consequently, the free energies needs reducing and in this case it means that you have to reduce the input of the colouring lanes, which results in a decrease in uncertainty, unexpected surprise, thus accidental errors can be avoided. Conscious learning of the rule and consistent attention are prerequisites for a successful solution, and the new pattern helps to solve increasingly difficult work sheets. At this point, the fact that the method allows increasingly difficult or complex work sheets to be created without changing the rule, or else the solution process, is extremely important.

In conclusion, the HappyLanesColor colouring method works in practice like a map for processing image information. The process can also be followed step by step depending on what emotional, psychical, and cognitive state you are. If our method is compared with the free creative processes, e.g. like the ones art therapy applies, from this point of view, the difference is to be found at this point. In fact, this method facilitates that emotional and cognitive processes operate simultaneously and in a complex way within a dynamic system. The process of information processing and problem solving and the psychical processes work together and both ensure the achievement of an optimal level of equilibrium. This way, this dynamic effect gets much stronger!

To summarize how colouring lanes work: First, they create a colouring task like images in an image. As their shape, orientation, and complexity can be flexibly altered related to the more and more complex drawings, you can create more and more complex tasks. So they ensure the order of difficulty of the tasks. Finally, by showing the colour of the details of the drawing, they both help and complicate the solution. If it is clear during the solution what colour you need to fill in a shape with, then they do not need to "help", but in the case of a more complex problem, you can go step-by-step based on their instructions.

Thus, the rule, i.e. the rule of the colouring lanes fully adapts to your abilities, your current state, and thus provides a deep, balanced mental state for the task at hand.

Now the different types of worksheet will be summarized.

Chapter 2.

Worksheet types

First, we report on two groups of worksheets engaged in the process by groups of children. These groups were created on the basis of the development of the way children think. The most basic method is when small children assign information they consider to be related into small groups (figure 1.) When they are faced with new information, they analyse whether it can be assigned into one of the known groups or whether a new group should be created. They create

sequences of inter-related information, separate exceptions out of which they create a new group. They arrange pieces of information into an order, highlighting differences – smaller, larger, more, less, etc.

The first group of work sheets presents an opportunity for this kind of reasoning.

Figure 1. The easiest worksheet for the early childhood

The drawings are easy to comprehend, lightly differentiated, and the drawing details include identical, similar and different-, according to their colours - shapes and sizes. Their inter-relations are characteristic; the repetition of the shapes in sequences may be detected. Of course, these systems no longer facilitate simple sequence creation, although it is interesting to see how the two operate parallel and how they shift from one another depending on which solution is the most practical for children. The shift may often be detected also within a single worksheet. Therefore it is not easy to draw a line between the two large types of work sheets. Instead, we seek to provide children the opportunity to freely make use of both.

Later, some really interesting solutions to this task and their analysis are going to be presented.

The other group of work sheets (figure 2.) on the other hand offer tasks that help the thinking skills in terms of comprehension of pictures by the help of more complex picture building; the rising number of drawing elements, and the increasingly complex relation of the colouring lanes to these elements.

Figure 2. Relatively complex worksheet

We follow with other series, indicating problems of space appearing, as the problems of shape – background, foreground – background. (figure 3.) Colouring lanes shift from one shape to another, breaking the parallel character of vertical lines, and they pose quite a task, because behind the colourful spots swirling on the surface, following the system of drawing shapes is a more difficult task for children. Basically, this series of work sheets prompts the question: how does our vision work, which shapes do we see as more dominate than others.

Figure 3. Foreground-background

There were worksheets where drawings are more clearly distinguishable, and colouring lanes only feature as reflections of the colours. But we can also find examples where we can hardly notice the drawings in the background, because the system of colouring lanes almost completely dominates the pictures. There is a series based on a similar principle, meaning the opposite drawing direction of drawings and colouring lanes, but in a special and specific context. The horizontal parallels of the colouring lanes and the crooked spots of waves squeeze against one another, serving to purpose fully develop children's ability to recognise the essence of pictures, as well as their spatial vision and ability to concentrate. (figure 4.) The waves can also be seen in the background of the small boat, thereby also posing the problem of foreground – background, shape – background.

Figure 4. The horizontal parallels of the colouring lanes and the crooked spots of waves

This appears in a different shape on the worksheet depicting a balloon where the crooked green spots of hills tower above each other and the horizontal – parallel spots of colouring lanes create the real task. (figure 5.) In the case of these tasks, of course, there are more drawing details and more attention must be paid to ensure that the final solution is indeed the complete picture.

Figure 5. The horizontal parallels of the colouring lanes and the crooked spots of hill

The next big step is the symmetry – mirror image series. The solution principle is naturally the same as always, but the tasks help in understanding, practicing and mastering the knowledge of symmetry – mirror image. (figure 6.)

Figure 6. Symmetry – mirror image

During the series of tasks, we can eventually find ourselves facing greater challenges, both has a result of the detail in the drawings and the more complicated appearance of colouring lanes. In this case, greater concentration ability, monotony endurance and sharper memory will be required from children. (figure 7.)

Figure 7. More and more details with complicated coloring lanes

Following the various approaches of spatial problems, we have arrived at the spatial imagery and understanding of geometrical shapes, with the help of dividing the squares into a number of smaller squares; (figure 8.)

Figure 8. Geometrical worksheets

Then to the work sheets with two- or more solutions, where the solution of the same worksheet could be several different pictures.

Figure 9. Worksheets with two or more solutions

Chapter 3. A complex functioning of colouring lanes

The code is determined by the object's outline combined with the colouring lanes.

The basic approach is to assess it either

1. as a task or
2. as an internal, closed-system model.

In the first approach (1) an external participant is required to solve the tasks, i.e., colour the worksheets. Thus, the operation of CL can be interpreted in the interaction between the task-solving actor and the task. It follows from the nature of the task that the process can be analyzed through the decision-making action of the task solver along active inference.

In the second (2) approach, the method is not interpreted as a task, therefore there is no task-solving external actor, thereby, the operation of the colouring lanes works in two approaches according to how the model is created.

First, a "creator" creates colouring lanes for drawings, (2.1) based on the 3 requirements or conditions, but also randomly, and secondly, (2.2) based on the principle of reduction, colouring lanes are created as a kind of visual codes, without the action of an external creator. According to the principle of reduction, the system of colouring lanes can be analyzed in macro or quantum environments, like along the minimization of free energy (FEP). After a brief introductory analysis, from this point on, this will be the main approach.

1. HappyLanesColor like a task.

The focus is, how the agent achieves perfect harmony and maximum behavioral synchronicity with the environment. Basically, we observe the process of perception in two approaches: according to neuropsychological and neurobiological approaches. and to the active inference. Berlyne's (1960) theory indicate that we always want to find the optimal arousal level: by increasing the novelty, complexity and variety of the stimuli in a person's environment, or by supply information that will reduce the individual's subjective uncertainty and discomfort. ,,

The active inference explains this process based on predictions/ and with couple of the perception and the action. We change our prediction to explain the sensory input through the perception; alternatively we change the sensory input to fulfill our prediction. This is a conflict between the action and the perception.

Thus, when we look at the diversive curiosity about the low stimuli level of the environment then we actually change the input to fulfill our prediction. Why? Because we must create prediction from the "empty" environment to increasing the level of the arousal but we must change the input to fulfill it! Alternatively, when we look at the specific curiosity about the high stimuli level of the environment then we actually change our prediction, that we can explain the input. The reason being that there is so much stimuli and one must create modified prediction to reduce the arousal level that can find and explain the input.

In other hand, the primary goal of the human being is to always attempt to achieve a state of equilibrium balance! In your current position and state, and according to your other abilities and perceptions at that specific moment. So then, how does this play out in a real situation with drawings and colouring lanes (below)? This task is related to your abilities, motivation, curiosity, your current emotional state and various other factors. You have, however, an overview of the whole picture and you can see, for example, that it depicts a building or a group of buildings. There are parts of the picture that are clearly visible and defined by a colour. You immediately realise that the colouring lanes on the roofs are red – so it is clear that all the missing parts of the roof (or white ones) should be filled in with red.

At the same time, some details are not blatantly obvious, and you thus need to check what the colouring lane suggests to you for the small details in larger pictures and shapes. The available information of the coloured parts is usually sufficiently enough to solve the issue. Sometimes, however, it may also be too difficult or just too easy as a challenge.

2.1 The role of external creators

In the case of colouring tasks, the colouring lanes get into the image from the outside, by the drawing hand of the "creator", in accordance with the 3 requirements.

First requirement: the colouring lanes should touch every detail of the drawing, so that when solving the task, it is possible to know which shape is which colour and with what colour to colour.

Second requirement: the colouring lanes should appear as continuous, unbroken spots in the drawing, as images in the image, showing the colours of different spaces as well (foreground-center-background, shape-background, etc.) according to pictures in picture principle.

Third requirement: a special connection between colouring lanes and drawings, whereby it is possible to create tasks of different levels and purposes. As a result, in the future, it will be possible to encode significantly more complex and quite complex systems, and it can also be applied to very small details, since quantitative criteria do not affect the operation of the method.

In addition to these three requirements, the creation of colouring lanes is only incidental and exclusively the work of artistic imagination, so several colouring lanes can be created for the same system.

2.2 Principle of reduction

The principle of colouring lanes can therefore be analysed through two basic approaches. Either a code is assigned to an image or object, creating a task and examining the behaviour of the person solving the task in a classical approach, which aims to achieve perfect synchronization with its environment, or CLP is perceived as pre-existent, as the maximum or upper limit of FEP, so to speak, Bayesian prediction error, and by reducing it, such as minimizing FEP, its lower limit, to the asymptotic limit, a marginal likelihood, i.e., the most optimal data is achieved. It can also be imagined that by deleting the discardable pixels of a bit image the most optimal code can be achieved by using this visual abstraction.

If colouring lanes would be able to work as a self-learning algorithm, as an intelligent label it would be able to encode the images/objects with their outlines. It would be a flexible method to find the most optimal size, form during it deletes the unnecessary pixels until the size, and form is exactly appropriate and carries all the data about the object. It moves with the object and if there occurs some change, the colouring lanes signal it and adapts to the changed object. Thus the code will be changed. We receive a new data label.

Colouring lanes scan continuously and send us the new data labels about the objects and their environment. In the same time it would be very useful to find and signal the mistakes in a repetitive system, where the routine image detection results in wrong decisions.

The dynamic operation of colouring lanes

In the following, I allowed myself a free simulation visual game, which is of course only a theoretical approach that cannot be a visual model of the theory. (Fields, C., Friston, K., Glazebrook, J. F., Levin, M. (2002). *A free energy principle for generic quantum systems*. Science Direct) Regardless, it was an exciting brainstorm for me, furthering the theory of how the colouring lanes work.

Scale-free models removing spacetime/background embedding and the assumption of “objective” or observer independent randomness. The variational FEP has been extended into an explanatory framework for living systems at all scales.

A classical “perfect predictor” achieves maximal classical correlation and hence maximal behavioural synchrony with its environment; it becomes a “perfect regulator” in the sense of the good regulator. Particles in quantum environment – QRF, spacetime-background freedom, scale-freedom, Bayesian observer in interaction with environment based on laws of active inference. The classical and quantum formulations of the FEP differ in their asymptotic behaviour, i.e., as total prediction error is driven toward zero.

FEP is compliant with the Principle of Unitarity and, conversely, that unitary evolution is compliant with the FEP. It allows us, in particular, to understand quantum context-switching as both a source of

prediction errors and a strategy for reducing prediction errors. Also allows us to view separability as a resource for classical communication and computation that is analogous to entanglement as a resource for quantum communication and computation.

This also applies to the dynamic operation of colouring lanes.

When a change occurs in an environment encoded by colouring lanes, the colouring lanes automatically transform and adapt to the change. In fact, a new colouring lane is created. This is always the source of forecasting errors.

However, the appropriate code created during this process reduces prediction errors, so it serves as a strategy for reducing prediction errors.

In the approach of the original colouring tasks, colouring lanes work along this logic. By putting them on the images, they create the conditions for predicted errors. That is, it is perceived as the maximum of FEP, the Bayesian prediction error.

However, colouring lanes provide a quasi-strategy for a correct solution, as they show the colour of shapes, thus reducing prediction errors. Thus, they can be perceived as the lower limit or minimalization of FEP.

The environment affecting the particle therefore causes a change in the internal state of the particle with a decrease in FEP. The internal state change has a counter effect on the environment, the change of which also affects the internal state of the particle. By moving FEP to the asymptotic limit, entanglement occurs in continuous interaction, where the environment also provides a reference framework and thus the prediction error is diverted towards zero.

Chapter 4. Schematism

During the subsequent analysis of the method and the ever-increasing variety of worksheets, it became clear that each image, regardless of its complexity, is made up of specifically defined elements. The elements can actually be illustrated by means of a very simple and suggestive 3x3 square. The basic elements are the following: the background and the objects, i.e. the details of the drawing and the colour, outline and shape of the colouring lane (s). These 9 elements, or else 9 numbers, define each colouring task.

	Color	Outline	Form
Background			
Object			
Coloring lane			

By means of this numeral system, you can describe any task and create new images based on the resulting numeral system, where the number of elements does not change, but you can still draw a whole new shape. You can see how many colouring lanes, how many colours, how many drawing details are included the picture, whether there is a background or not, and based solely on numbers you can compare different pictures to see if they are identical or not. It offers an interesting opportunity for you to finally create a colouring task based solely on the numeral system based on your own concepts and ideas.

Let's see the simplest task, showing a triangle with a blue colouring lane and with no background. The 3x3 square describes the picture very clearly. There is no background, so there is no colour, contour and shape. There is an object in the image, a triangle that has an outline

and a shape. You also have a colouring lane that has one colour, blue, an outline, and a shape. If you only see this 3x3 square, you can create countless colouring tasks based on it. There are three examples below the triangle, a square, a circle, and a board game figure that can be described by the same matrix.

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	Color	Outline	Form
Background	0	0	0
Object	1	1	1
Coloring lane	1	1	1

	Color	Outline	Form
Background	0	0	0
Object	11	11	11
Coloring lane	6	2	2

This figure is another example of how to create a whole new picture after describing the toy car in the numeral system. Each task consists of 11 objects; two colouring lanes show you the 6 colours and there is no background.

	<p>20 objects 3 colouring lanes</p> <p>0 0 0 20 20 20 2 3 3</p>
	<p>2 objects 1 colouring lane</p> <p>0 0 0 4 4 4 4 1 1</p>
	<p>11 objects 2 colouring lanes</p> <p>0 0 0 11 11 11 5 2 2</p>
	<p>11 objects 1 colouring lane</p> <p>0 0 0 11 11 11 6 1 1</p>
	<p>11 objects 2 colouring lanes</p> <p>0 0 0 11 11 11 6 2 2</p>

Different variations for practicing...

<div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-left: 100px;"> <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Colour</th> <th>Outline</th> <th>Form</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Background</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Object</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Colouring lane</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> </div>		Colour	Outline	Form	Background				Object				Colouring lane				<p>1 object 1 colouring lane + background without outline</p> <p style="text-align: right;">1 0 0 1 1 1 2 1 1</p>
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Object																	
Colouring lane																	
	<p>2 objects 1 colouring lane + background without outline</p> <p style="text-align: right;">1 0 0 2 2 2 3 1 1</p>																
	<p>3 objects 1 colouring lane + background without outline</p> <p style="text-align: right;">1 0 0 3 3 3 4 1 1</p>																
	<p>4 objects 1 colouring lane</p> <p style="text-align: right;">1 0 0 4 4 4 5 1 1</p>																
	<p>5 objects 1 colouring lane</p> <p style="text-align: right;">1 0 0 5 5 5 6 1 1</p>																

An interesting issue is when the colouring lane informs you on the background colour but there is no information on either the outline or shape. Maybe you can think of what happens when you look up at the infinite blue sky as a background ...?

	<p>1 object 1 coloring lane +background</p> <p>1 1 1 1 1 1 2 1 1</p>
	<p>2 objects 1 coloring lane +background</p> <p>1 1 1 2 2 2 3 1 1</p>
	<p>3 objects 1 coloring lane +background</p> <p>1 1 1 3 3 3 4 1 1</p>
	<p>4 objects 1 coloring lane +background</p> <p>1 1 1 4 4 4 5 1 1</p>
	<p>5 objects 1 coloring lane +background</p> <p>1 1 1 5 5 5 6 1 1</p>

The same set of tasks but with a limited background.

	Color	Outline	Form
Background	0	0	0
Object	66	66	66
Coloring lane	7	3	3

In fact, any of the images can be defined in this numeral system, or it can be used to create a new image. In this case, any image without a background, consisting of 66 objects, in 7 colours and 3 colouring lanes can be created, as you wish.

Chapter 5.
HappyLanesColor and children

"Blue is blue, yellow is yellow, red is red. That's all!"- Sarah, 4.

Diverse, imaginative, free creative activities are very important for the development of young children. From state-of-the-art tools available for purchase to drawing in the sand with a stick, children see virtually every opportunity to give way to their inner urge of self expression.

Behind an activity there is always synchronised and concentrated reasoning. My favourite example is when you ask children to draw a picture of autumn. In this case, they must first consider the following issues:

1. what are the seasons, what distinguishes them from one another and what makes autumn different compared to other seasons. Colours, shapes, experiences, memories and impressions appear in front of their minds' eyes.
2. The next step is to decide on the visual elements they consider the most expressive of autumn, so you need to reconsider all the features, your their own knowledge.
3. After that, they have to decide which one to choose, i.e. what do they want to draw?
4. Of course, they need to select graphic tools for this. Paint? Thin or thick brush? Colour-pencils? Large-size paper?
5. Finally, they need to design the image they want to draw or paint.

Thereby, children consider five different approaches when they want to present autumn, which greatly helps them deepen their knowledge. Therefore, creative and visual activities, in addition to their emotionally liberating effect, also have significant cognitive benefits and facilitate effective learning.

HLC method is also associated with this trend, except that a rule is integrated into the system. Recognizing all the benefits of free creative activity, the essence of my method is that, in addition to or besides being based on visual fantasy and creativity, it has powerful cognitive content. For all this, a rule; the rule of the colouring lanes, is the tool. If one follows it flexibly and dynamically he or she will have the opportunity to think through the solution. By having to consider the information they have about autumn several times and in different ways in order to create an image in the end, in this case, this process of repeating takes a different approach. While colouring an image, as the details are connected to the large whole and every detail gets into its right place, information also traverses complex paths through your brain. Good examples of this are the various exciting colouring anatomy books that use the same principle. In fact, by associating learning with an activity, i.e. with a kind of task solving, knowledge will be much easier to acquire and more lasting. It is because it enters your brain's information processing unit in many different ways. Especially when the activity involved is emotionally soothing, it relaxes and it generates useful mental images.

When you look at a colouring sheet that has a flower scribbled with colouring lanes, you can still see that it is a flower. Your brain perceives and processes it step by step based on its details, and stores it according to the approach of the above research. Then, as the problem is being solved, your mind will be constantly revolving around the flowers. Each detail, the small leaves, the petals, the yellow seedbed, will trigger thousands and thousands of associations in you. Mental images circulate in your brain, but like a complex, full picture of flowers. Meanwhile, with the accurate colouring of the details, thanks to the information processing mechanism, the image of the details is constantly trying to find its place; the parts are connected to the whole, and the original image is built up step by step. Thus both processes, which are capable of creating mental images, work in parallel during the problem solving. After this lengthy and exhaustive analysis, you may be not surprised if I say that there is a deafening silence during the colouring sessions.

Of course, the HappyLanesColor colouring method is primarily meant for children. The goal is to provide them a challenge where they can choose images of as many variations as possible on a wide variety of subjects, styles and levels of difficulty. Over the years we have worked with children in numerous kindergartens, schools and were involved in various children's programs and experience has clarified the main methodological points. Of course, in addition to this, based on further special educational and development goals, the method can be used flexibly, which gives teachers great freedom. In the following, we analyse the 4 most important methodological steps, such as motivation, free choice of tasks, solution strategies, and control.

Motivation

"Kids are visual creatures in a visual world." Rober Fisher

Young children think in images before they learn to read and write. They are surrounded by a visual world and are therefore extremely responsive in visual sense. As a result, despite the fact that we adults think HappyLanesColor colouring sheets are confusing because they look as if they were scribbled and it is difficult to make heads or tails of them, kids act just the opposite of what is expected. They can see what the picture represents and also know immediately how to colour it. They recognize the rule. One of my most important experiences over the years is that they should not be given any instructions on how to solve the problem. Because they know it. You must colour the image with the specified colours. Because the worksheets are colourful, interesting, and the original image is only visible if all details are properly coloured with the colour provided, it all arouses their curiosity and motivates them to colour the sheet. In many cases, it includes even children who usually skip the drawing-colouring jobs or who can't concentrate on a task for a long time sitting in one place. It's beneficial if they can see all the worksheets and where they can get to. They have to be given a chance. Let us not decide for them what they are capable of. Even though worksheets can be as hard as it gets, let us give the kids a chance to surprise us.

I have had positive experiences in countless cases, despite the fact that my method was considered strange by many. In fact, children are not aware of what we expect regarding their abilities. They are frankly and instinctively open to all influences that come from the world and try to navigate amongst them in their own way and in their own rhythm. And the colouring method offers them a chance to follow this instinct in the most varied form. The chance to be obvious. This is truly a motivating force.

A Free choice of task

It is a crucial step and closely linked to the issue of motivation. You see, a wide variety of worksheets are designed specifically to help everyone find their favourite topic, an interesting, task offering the right level of difficulty. It is up to the kids to decide which one to choose.

This freedom is very important, because the method is actually a tool for getting to know themselves freely, and becoming aware of their own abilities. Whether they choose a colouring sheet that is easy or too difficult, it will definitely be an important experience for them. There is no rating, no "classification", no compulsion to conform. Every small child can try himself or herself, and become aware of his or her own limits without any consequence. If they don't succeed, it is not a problem, because they know that it is part of the game. Awareness is a crucial component of the whole program. All physiological phenomena accompanying the process of solution process should be known to the children. With this method, they can learn how to handle it and develop it consciously later on. Therefore, it is not a traumatic or failure experience to make a mistake or fail to colour a worksheet. However, the opposite is also true

if one is too careful and chooses a much easier image. In any case, the order of difficulty allows everyone to move one step higher after a successful solution. (figure 10.)

Figure 10. Worksheets are according to the level of the difficulty

But let's analyse the issue of the free choice of tasks in a bit more detail through an example. I was in a free class with the kids where I hand carried lots and lots of worksheets and they were scattered all over the desk. Everyone could take what they wanted and as many as they wanted. A little boy picked a worksheet with a red car, which is a vibrant image, as if it was really moving. When this sheet was coloured by the kids, it really did feel as if the car had stopped. So the little boy started colouring the picture and told an incredible story about how nearly his entire family died when their car caught fire in their yard. Luckily the case did not end up in

tragedy, no one was injured, the fire was extinguished, but he was still frightened and he "remembered" it ever since. In the following, we are going to analyse the background to the free choice of tasks based on the above extreme example using another simulated event.

Imagine that a car falls off a high bridge in front of you. Let's examine the following 8 aspects whereby the impact of the event you can be assessed.

1. your current general emotional state
2. your previous experience
3. your knowledge
4. whether you are emotionally connected to the event
5. your distance from the event
6. the content aspects of the event
7. the intensity of the event
8. the speed at which we are affected

The **first aspect** shows how vulnerable, insecure, or emotionally weak you are in that specific moment. How strong you are to handle this effect. The **second aspect** shows whether you had had a similar experience in your life. If you have, you have some experience of how you can handle and process the current event. In the **third aspect**, we can analyse how it can help you if you better understand what happened. Or what happens when you have an experience that you do not understand at all. The **fourth aspect** is very critical, because it does not matter whether you are emotionally attached to who or what this accident is about. The **fifth aspect** is the distance. Are you at the spot or you witness the event indirectly, e.g. through television. The **sixth aspect** describes the true content of the event. The **seventh aspect** is the degree of intensity. By this we mean a kind of drama that is made up of the event but also by your participation as an observer. The **eighth aspect** is the speed of the event. How fast the event takes place? Almost barely visible? Did it occur in an instant and completely unexpectedly? Or it was long enough to keep you in anxiety all along? Could you hope that the car wouldn't fall down after all? Or was it just long enough for you to understand what was going to happen, what was going on, and you could witness it happening?

Recalling the boy's case, based on these eight aspects, it seems that he was in a balanced, stable state of mind at the time the incident occurred, that he experienced it with his family who solved the problem, and have been talking it over and over again, so they have managed to process it fortunately. The little boy told me about it, and it was evident that he still had to talk about it a lot, and he did not pick this particular colouring task. He had no previous experience of this kind, so the novelty increased the impact of the event, but made it a bit less severe as well because he did not realise that that care could have exploded within a matter of minutes. The emotional attachment to the participants of the event was very strong because his beloved family was involved! The distance from the event was very short as they were near the car in the yard. The content aspects amplified the effect because he was not that small any more, therefore he could understand the implications in case the fire had not been extinguished quickly. But he wasn't big enough to recognize the possibility of an explosion. The intensity of the event

was very high based on the values of the above aspects. And it was dramatic because it happened quite unexpectedly. They were chatting peacefully, but just a moment later a tragedy had almost happened. Beyond the first moment of fright, the family immediately joined their forces and worked together to extinguish the fire, which they managed to. For the little boy, this, in addition to being a dramatic event, this was definitely a success! A memorable moment of keeping together.

In this case, this example is also instructive because the time it took to solve the task gave the boy a chance to rethink, re-live the event, and talk about it. When analysing the operation of colouring lanes, we have seen how information in our brain searches for interfaces, how predictions move between different hierarchical levels, and what processes take place during the problem solving in order to find equilibrium. Consequently, in such a situation, colouring the car provided every opportunity to the little boy to recall the event, to talk about it and interpret every moment of it once more.

Figure 11. A little boy choosing a task

We have analysed this extreme example in such detail to illustrate the true significance of the process of free choice and problem solving.

Free choice of tasks can also be briefly summarized in the following approach, according to how a small child can select the most appropriate task for himself.

The level of activity is very high - the solution is wrong: an overselected task (figure 12.)

The task sparked the curiosity of the children, motivated them emotionally and cognitively, but they could not solve it properly. They overselect the task, were unable to focus and pay attention, which could have many reasons. Many routine errors were made during the solution, or they were not able to complete it entirely.

Figure 12. A solution for the overselected task

The level of activity is very low - the solution is correct: an underselected task (figure 13.)

The task was underselected, the solution did not require too much activity, the result is correct. Incorrect identification of one's own abilities.

Figure 13. A solution for the underslected task

Level of activity is very low - the solution is wrong: avoiding behaviour, overselected task (figure 14.)

There is a high probability that they have chosen a much more difficult task than they can solve, which is why the level of activity is very low and the result will not be satisfactory. The task is too difficult, so the fear of failure has discouraged the children. A typical example of a poster room. Avoiding behaviour.

Figure 14. A solution for the avoiding behaviour

Level of Activity is very high - the solution is correct /appropriately-selected task (figure 15.)

This is the ideal state when the right task triggers the right activity and the solution is successful.

Figure 15. Correct solution

Solution strategies

The children could decide themselves regarding the solution of the task. They choose a colouring sheet and colour it to their liking. But there are more opportunities in the program. The colouring a worksheet can be completed according to several solution principles. It is a matter of approach. From top to bottom? Or right-to-left? Or by colour? Or the windows first and then the walls of the house? Or the houses in the foreground first, and then the shapes of the background, so that the spaces are visually distinguished during colouring? (figure 16.)

Figure 16. Different solution strategies

In fact, every worksheet is different, so you can always come up with new order of solutions. The key is to figure it out together with the kids and then stick to the itinerary that you set. Children can learn a lot from this; they can practice consistent task solving and acquire the ability to focus which will be beneficial for their later study is. They can get a kind of routine that they will be grateful for later.

As the difficulty aspect is one of the most important elements of the method, there are worksheets that require this very ability of being able to follow a solution strategy consistently. For images with two or more solutions, it is very important that the decision whereby the blue house is in the foreground and the yellow one is behind it in the background, should not “be broken” i.e. the whole building should be in the foreground during colouring, and not a part of it in the foreground while other parts in the background. In order the children to be able to solve such a problem skilfully, it is important to improve their memory, concentration, ability to endure monotony, perseverance, creative vision, imagination, and they should be able to figure out other solutions while colouring. In short, it requires a well-structured training. Actually, what is the difference compared to having to solve a long mathematical equation? Countless of accidental errors can occur in both cases. The method provides an opportunity to prepare for this challenge. (You can see two solutions, but there are significantly more solutions are available).

Control

The ability of children to solve the task and their success depends greatly on their ability to control their own work. They definitely need to master this method either individually, or in groups or else while controlling each other's work. As one of the most important features of colouring sheets is that they are made up of more and more details, children have to pay attention to more and more correlations, so there are more and more things to be controlled. It takes a lot of practice, and requires lot of help to be able to schedule their time needed for completing the task in the future, and still have time for control as well, and on the other hand,

be able to experiment so that they could find the most appropriate method for themselves, develop the "knowledge", experience and ability needed for all that. Indeed, this is the really „stressful” part of the problem solving process. Going over and checking what you've finally done from the beginning. Checking what is ready at last. Besides, the time it takes is almost as long as the time one has devoted to the solution. This is why there are several solutions. Let's figure them out together with the kids. For example, you don't have to leave it all to the end. You can also proceed by blocks after blocks. When a part of the house is done, it's easier to check that part than the whole picture at the end. Not so overwhelming, and there are less possibility ignoring mistakes. You can also follow your chosen solution strategy during the control. So if you progress by colour and let's say you're done with yellow, check it out. Quite often it also good proves to be a good idea to work with a partner and exchange their jobs to check whether there are any mistakes. It is an interesting phenomenon, but when you have someone else's task in hand, you are more aware of mistakes than in case of your own. (Remember? New inputs stimulate your brain!) It can also be useful to project the worksheets in larger size and "hunt down" the mistakes or missed parts that we haven't noticed and missed together. In our case, this is merely a playful practice, with lots of conversations, but it has very promising effects for the future. Especially, if it is emphasized in advance, how very important awareness is. Children need to know exactly what they are doing, and why they are doing it. It's a joint effort for their own interest. Our goal is to internalize the ability to control, so that later the question whether they should do it or not would not even occur. It will have a great significance later, during the scary era of school assessments.

Chapter 6.

Analysing the mistakes

Now let's take a look at a few examples of typical mistakes. We analyse one or two “incorrectly” completed worksheets in more detail. These errors have a moral for us, because they help give some glimpse into the unique thinking of children and cast a light on the way in which this method provides an opportunity for us to do so.

A 4-5 year old girl coloured this worksheet (figure 17.) in two ways and if she had continued, there would likely have been more and more different solutions. She handled the above problem on the first worksheet in a similar way, but she manipulated with green colour, colouring the area between the two wheels of the car green, so that the green shape of the trailer would have a match on the picture. Thus, she did not consider it necessary to colour the black shape of the rear wheel. The match for the black shapes was already present in the picture, engulfing the green shape, which also had its pair on the trailer.

Figure 17. An example of the special solutions worksheet

It was interesting to see how, after completing this work, the little girl started to colour the same worksheet once again, though nobody suggested her to do so. We could see that her approach was totally different. She used completely new approaches for this new solution (figure 18.).

Figure 18. An example of the special solutions

The previous train of thought was no longer of interest to her, she coloured the bottom part including the wheels as she had to, based on the colouring lanes, however, the top half of the car, which she had had no particular interest in during the first solution and which she coloured correctly based on the colouring lanes in the first solution, was given a whole new meaning. The horizontal division of colouring lanes and their system of building onto one another provided the opportunity of forming series. The interchanging of yellow and blue colouring lanes appears in a completely new form, by the creation of a counter-point. The blue-yellow division of the top colouring lane, moving from left to right appears in her presentation, in the line to be coloured in the blue yellow blue yellow series, if we look at it within the system of windows. But we can also look at this exceptional and genius solution from top to bottom as well. Next the blue of the top colouring lane is followed by a yellow patch in the lane to be coloured, which then is followed by another blue colouring lane.

Figure 19.

The most important shape from the point of view of my analysis is the yellow ochre colour of the sailboat on the left, behind the wave depicted with dark green colour, and another dark green wave to the right of this one. The horizontal – parallel colouring lane runs along the the waves and selects the light green colour which should be used for colouring the missing sections of the wave. (Figure 20.) But during the solution of the worksheet, this shape became so dominant for the small child that she followed the horizontal line and instead of the yellow ochre and dark green, she coloured this whole section with light green. Nevertheless, she understood the essence of the task, because starting from the bottom all the way up to this point, she completed the worksheet perfectly.

Figure 20. Horizontal parallel colouring lanes and waves

Of course, if you are aware of this phenomenon, you can develop your ability to handle it consciously. When the visual image of numbers, letters, texts overwrite the real information, you experience it as a small negligence, even though an important physiological process is behind your strange decision. The real assessment of children's abilities and school

performance often depends on these so-called routine errors, too, and sometimes the grades do not reflect their true knowledge and abilities.

Chapter 7.

A HappyLanesColor and Neuroaesthetics

The principle of colouring lanes, i.e. is, the principle of image in image, can move you to more remote areas. To do this, however, you need to recall important antecedents from the world of science. Rudolph Arnheim's example considered to be a classic by today raises fundamental questions. (figure 21.)

Figure 21. Rudolph Arnheim's figure

Because what can you see in the picture? Do you see a white circle on a black square? Or a black square on a white background with a circular hole in the centre? What does your choice of variation depend on? Which shape do you find dominant?

What happens when the colours are swapped? Or if the shapes are repainted in different colours, the way Andy Warhol did in his infamous works. Of course, we are not looking for answers now, everyone can see what and how they see in this case.

Recently, brain research has found exciting areas regarding vision that has been utilized to a high degree in neuroaesthetics, neuromarketing, and artificial intelligence. Of course, this cannot be discussed without exploring some history of art.

The visual messages of fine art have created complex code systems for centuries; they created a completely unique language. We have accumulated a great deal of knowledge with their help, creating this vast and complex set that is bound to all elements of the system with its countless units. This network, just like the neural network of our brains, stores almost uncodable knowledge that man has incorporated into newer and newer works of art, enriching the boundless artistic intellect. The science of aesthetics takes an interesting approach to the early stages of Western Christian culture, namely Coptic painting, later called Pre-Raphaelite. It is called a-mimetic, that is, non-depicting, or one that does not imitate reality. It does not directly interpret the world of form, but the intellectual system of the age can reach us through a system of symbols that has been developed for centuries. It draws an interesting parallel to the art of Austrian Art Nouveau, also called a-mimetic, and extraordinary, which also began to communicate through a unique system of symbols. (*The Age of Insight: The Quest to Understand the Unconscious in Art, Mind, and Brain, from Vienna 1900 to the Present*)

It summarizes the artistic articulations of selected, bygone ages whereby it expresses its own age in a unique way. Art Nouveau articulates in a complex manner and returns to a kind of cohesion, the conscious need for a full expression of the age. The history of art is an incredibly exciting quest, and every artist's oeuvre leaves a trace, a sign that creates a mosaic with the signs of the other artists, which gives rise to new artistic thoughts and special brush strokes. Taking a look at a seventeenth-century painting today, one thing is for certain: the people appear as characters in the painting cannot live in our age. You cannot see the characters of our age in

the pictures. And that's not because of the environment, or because they wear contemporary clothes. Nowadays in the world of theatre and cinema this should not be a problem. Their character, their features are different. Paintings capture the age at which they are created. They set biblical themes amongst a scenery of their own buildings, contemporary subject matters come to life in their everyday life, and their own people are the characters in the stories depicted. They do not place Jesus in the Middle East desert and in his living environment, but he is set to the painting's own age instead so that it could address the contemporary audience. Painting updates. It strives for clarity and drama, and a perfect representation of it is a prerequisite to achieve this. If the history of art is traced from Coptic depictions to Titian's works, it can be seen that the artist were driven by the quest for achieving technical brilliance, the perfection of imitation of reality, which peaked at the unrivalled realization of hyperrealism. But a lot has happened in the meantime. The achievements that the academies have routinely taught to gifted apprentices always became obsolete and scarce. More and more young artists were coming, who simply had to study and master the accomplished results and technical feats, as compulsory part of their training, but for them, they were only obstacles to free expression. And so on and so forth. In this swirling stream, it is really difficult to find the right proportion and balance between motivations for expressing the content and formal experimentation. The rotation of complete demolition of traditions and of new constructions reached the black and white square of Kazimir Malevich, which was the artistic expression of total reduction.

You can truly understand its significance when you have seen, **loki**, or not really liked a lot of things in this wonderful human development called art history. So, returning to the Austrian Art Nouveau, it can be seen that it is an almost completely unique and educational artistic island, unlike anything else. They have captured their own ideals of their own era, yet their way of articulation and stylized environments still allow for the exploration of rich historical associations. Complex associations that in the traditional sense are almost impossible to be translated to the known figurative elements. When one sees the pictures he or she have only feelings and impressions. The viewer is involved in the feeling of "it is like ...". No wonder that it has become the focus of research in the field of neuroscience and artificial intelligence. A picture in a picture. Or a picture behind a picture. Message and expression. A higher and more sophisticated level of encoding a message into images, which is essential to perfectly simulate the procedure of information processing by the human brain.

After this somewhat lengthy introduction, let us analyse what significance the above bears for our the approach of our method. The starting point is the same as our slogan: picture in picture. The system of colouring lanes in a picture is like another picture. But what could this other picture be? Actually, anything. Beyond its essential "colouring lane " function, any image can be. It can express anything. It can convey messages of "it's like a ...". Complex associations that evoke deep thoughts.

Figure 22. Lilly Martin Spencer, *Medieval fruit still life melons, pears, blue grapes* 1859; Oil, canvas, 34,5 x 45,5 cm; rewritten – Mondrian

The picture above shows an interesting transcript. The starting point is a still life. The picture was redrawn by the outlines of the fruits, but the true message or association is Mondrian's art. Therefore, the colouring lanes perform this function and are drawn on the image. (the colouring sheet is just a sketch for illustration) You can see the fruits in the picture, but when you first look at it, your brain will evoke fashionable and much-seen contemporary artwork. It recalls well-known colours, shapes and you find yourself in Mondrian's artistic world. Of course, when you colour the image, the illusion disappears and a schematic transcript of the original still life emerges. But it's a long procedure, and your brain will take you into Mondrian's world with every decision you make. How does this all happen? What are you going through throughout? Maybe it's not a conscious process. You can't remember Mondrian's name, you can't list his works, you just know that you have something similar somewhere. Illusion? Deceit? Or just a little reminder? The intricate encoding of visual information raises exciting questions.

Paintings to “timelessness” of the eras

Middle Ages - painting by Éva Szűts-Nowsky 2025.

Art Nouveau - painting by Éva Szűts -Nowsky 2025.

Saint Sebastian - painting by Éva Szűts-Nowsky 2025.

Digital graphics by Éva Szűts-Nowsky

Chapter 8.

A HappyLanesColor and Neuromarketing

If we take this further on, the modern world of neuromarketing manipulates with similar simulations. But is it a modern phenomenon? If, for example, you review how Western culture depicted religion, you can notice similar moments. The simplest symbols and pictures began to communicate biblical stories clearly on the walls of temples in Western culture, in the easily recognizable style of modern logos. The most important events were made "readable" for the masses who could not read the Bible. Today, the visual image of a product is so clear and familiar to you that you can reach for it on the shelves without thinking, even though there are countless similar products. A powerful and clear visual image has burned into your brain, which works even when it appears not in its our usual environment, i.e., in the stores.

It also has the same effect on images, ads, videos and movies. The better, the more expressive, the more memorable this visual world is, the more successful it will be. Just as in the past, the

strongest emotions a fresco evoked, the more dramatically it expressed e.g. Christ's suffering, the more the painter was paid. Especially in the era of counter-reformation. But the world fashion is also an interesting example for that. It gets inspiration from an endless array of patterns accumulated to date and connects them in exciting new variations. And you find yourselves in them somewhere and somehow and make a choice. Your decision is the result of a complicated process, and you can think it over once after buying something why you chose that particular item in the mall where millions of stimuli tried to influence you.

Wrong spelling as ADIL instead of ALDI but we can recognize the word ALDI because the colours, the font well-known. Can we see the city drawing behind the word? (figure 23.)

Figure 23. ALDI logo

Iconic shapes as drawing form or coloring lanes

The colouring sheet above thus provides an illustrative example of neuromarketing approach. Nesquik brand is featured in the colour scheme of the colouring lanes. To make our example even more powerful, we've inserted photos of other products next to it.

One of the most important benefits is the time you spend solving the task. The more interfaces formed between the information, the more powerful the effect of the input will be. In other words, the fact that not only a passive reception of an image takes place, but it is accompanied by complex, emotional and cognitive activity, you are much more likely to store it as lasting "memory" in your brain. The new data takes their place in relation to the stored levels and your brain works in the routine version compared to the stored levels, which means it is energy efficient. A routine image will pop up, e.g. just like the picture of Nesquik chocolate picture on the colouring sheet above. (figure 24.)

Just to prove the above, here is an example of how branding uses the success of a brand to sell its own no-name product with similar packaging.

Figure 24. Nesquik brand

Chapter 9.

Epilogue

Further Thought Experiments

Models, games for artificial intelligence – image identification, coding, data labelling “Data labelling is not a task, it requires lots of skills, knowledge and lots of effort to label the data for machine learning training. And for visual perception model needs annotated images to train the computer vision algorithm helping the model to recognize the various objects recognizable. However, while labelling the different types of data companies encounter various problems making the labelling tasks more time taking and ineffective. To make the data labelling more effective and productive we need to understand these problems. So, in this

blog post, we will discuss data labelling challenges with few suggestions to overcome such problems.” <https://www.analytics.ai/blog/top-data-labeling-challenges-faced-by-annotation-companies/> If “colouring lanes” would able to work as a self-learning algorithm, as an intelligent label it would able to encode the images/objects with their outlines. It would be a flexible method to find the most optimal size, form during it deletes the unnecessary pixels until the size, and form is exactly appropriate and carries all the data about the object. It moves with the object and if there occurs some change, the “colouring lanes” signal it and adapts to the changed object. Thus the code will be changed. We receive a new data labels. “Colouring lanes” scans continuously and send us the new data labels about the objects and their environment. In the same time it would be very useful to find and signal the mistakes in a repetitive system, where the routine image detection results wrong decisions. “Colouring lanes” finds the most optimal forms, size

Figure 25. Different variations of “colouring lanes”

Perception

https://mersz.hu/dokumentum/matud202206__12/

Experimental models to automatic change detection, event-related potential, visual mismatch negativity in relationship with movement

The essence of this approach is, does the perception experiment tell us a new solution result if the subject also has to solve a cognitive task, i.e. make a decision?

How the solution changes in mirror of

1. How long is the green color visible?
2. Is movement also detectable during observation?
3. How much time was available to learn and practice the rule before?
4. How many places does the color green appear within a model?
5. The size of the green shape – how dominant?

Question: How visually perceptive is the person who solves the experimental task?

Are there any disturbing circumstances?

What are the fundamental internal mental and psychological states at a given moment?

Evaluation problems: there is only one way to solve the series of task, so all influencing factors must be precisely formulated.

How will the test subject decide in connect with the movement?

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